

MAIN ERRORS SOURCES IN GEOMAGNETIC MEASUREMENTS AT THE AIA OBSERVATORY OF ANTARCTIC AKADEMIK VERNADSKY STATION

M. Leonov

State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center, Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; g60s1981@gmail.com

Among the main modern priorities in geomagnetic measurements is the need to rely on physical realities and reduce possible errors to a minimum. The basic formula that describes the result of geomagnetic measurements by the mandatory set of instruments consisting of a variometer and a standard scalar magnetometer, recommended by the INTERMAGNET network, is the sum of two vectors (of the Earth's main magnetic field and of variation). From the point of view of achieving maximum measurement accuracy, it makes sense to consider the most influential factors of variations that are capable of introducing errors into the measured value of the induction vector of the Earth's main magnetic field at Vernadsky and that can be detected by their morphological features.

The main factors include the secular drift of the geomagnetic poles and the daily "deformation" of the magnetosphere due to its "blowing" by the solar wind. Simplification of a real physical process by its mathematical representation can lead to measurement errors.

The main error is that the variation vector is not coplanar with the Earth's main field vector if the "induction operating point" vector of the variometer does not coincide with the main magnetic field vector. In fact, the space-time variations are measured by the variometer relative to selected points, which are set by the stabilized compensation currents on the geomagnetic field component sensors. It can be argued that the overall measurement accuracy depends on the degree of mismatch between the "induction operating point" vector and the undistorted main field vector.

The continuous development of modern digital geomagnetic measuring equipment, measurement methods and data processing is rapidly advancing towards ensuring measurements with high accuracy and reliability.

It can be argued that among the most significant links that can generate the greatest errors, we should first of all note the absolute observations, as well as the operation of selecting and setting the "working point" of the variometer (that is, the vector of the "induction working point" of the variometer).